

METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF BUDGET EXPENDITURE PLANNING IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In the article considers the theoretical foundations of the formation of budget expenditures, its significance and classification, studies the essence and principles of budget planning, and analyzes the main methods of budget expenditure planning.

Keywords: budget planning, budget expenses, planning methods, normative regulation.

Introduction. Budget expenditures represent the leading link of the state's financial system. They occupy an important place in the political and economic life of any country. Budget relations are relations between bodies of any level of power of the budget system concerning the issues of consolidation and differentiation of budget powers, as well as compliance with all rights and obligations, responsibility in the field of budget preparation, approval, execution and budget processes. Thanks to the budget, any state can focus financial resources on the most important areas of social and economic development, use the budget as an instrument of state regulation of the economy.

Budget expenditures are monetary funds that are directed to the financial support of the functions and tasks of state administration and local self-government. Budget expenditures play a crucial role in regulating the country's economy.

The structure and amount of budget expenditures are influenced by many factors:

- the state structure;
- state policy (external and internal)
- the general level of the economy;
- the level of welfare of the population, etc. Budget expenditures are of great

importance in solving social problems. Many important branches of social services for citizens (health care, education, social security) are financed from the budget.

Budget expenditure planning helps the state to assess the state of economic development, taking into account the role of budget expenditures and its impact on various aspects of management, since the country's expenditures contribute to the renewal of production assets, the development and implementation of advanced scientific achievements in production.

The economic essence of budget expenditures is manifested in numerous types of expenditures. Each of them has both quantitative and qualitative characteristics.

The qualitative characteristic reflects the economic nature and allows you to determine the purpose of budget expenditures. The quantitative characteristic allows you to determine their value.

The variety of types of budget expenditures is due to the following factors - уровень the level of socio-economic development of the state; - the branching links between the budget and the national economy; - the administrative and territorial structure of the country; - the forms of providing budget resources, etc.

The combination of these factors leads to a particular system of budget expenditures of any country at all stages of socio-economic development.

In order to determine the role and significance of budget expenditures in economic life, a classification is carried out according to some characteristics. The use of data that are grouped by elements of the budget classification allows you to see the actual picture of the movement of budget funds and influence economic and social processes [2]. Comparison of planned and reporting indicators, analysis and comparison of relevant data provide an opportunity to draw conclusions and recommendations on the use of budget funds, the direction of the main cash flows for economic and social development [3].

According to the role in social reproduction, budget expenditures are divided into two parts: the first part is related to the development of material production, the improvement of its sectoral structure, the second part is used for the maintenance and further development of the non-production sphere.

According to the economic content, current and capital budget expenditures can be distinguished. Current expenses are the part of expenses that ensures the current functioning of state authorities, budget institutions, local self-government bodies, and other expenses that are not included in capital expenditures [2].

Capital expenditures are a part of budget expenditures that provides investment and innovation activities and other expenses aimed at expanding reproduction, during which property is created and increased [2; 8].

The grouping of budget expenditures by their public purpose reflects the functions performed by the state - economic, social, defense, etc.

Of great importance is the functional classification of budget expenditures, reflecting the areas of public activity to which funds are directed. At the same time, all

expenses are divided into the following major sections: 1) national issues; 2) national defense; 3) national security and law enforcement; 4) national economy; 5) housing and communal services; 6) environmental protection; 7) education; 8) culture, cinematography, mass media; 9) health and sports; 10) social policy; 11) inter-budget transfers.

This classification clearly reflects the role of the state in various sectors of society.

In the designated groups of expenses, additional expenses may be allocated for the implementation of the most important national programs. The allocation of funds for certain types of targeted programs ensures the priority concentration of budget funds and their use in the most important areas that are provided

for by state authorities. Each of the above groups of expenses can be divided by target and departmental characteristics.

According to the target feature, you can consider expenses that are divided into specific costs. Classification according to the intended purpose helps to use budget funds rationally, it is the basis for the production of effective control over the use of budget investments [3]. According to the departmental feature, the corresponding ministry, other legal entity or state institution that receives budget investments is allocated in each group of expenses. This feature of the classification of budget expenditures shows changes in the structure of expenditures that are associated with changes in the management system [3; 9].

According to the territorial basis, budget expenditures are divided into: 1) expenditures of the federal budget; 2) expenditures of the budgets of the subjects of the federation; 3) expenditures of local budgets.

The classification allows you to compare expenses according to budget performance reports. This contributes to the economical spending of funds, compliance with financial discipline, as well as control over the implementation of the financial plan.

According to their content, the norms of budget law are divided into material and procedural. Material norms establish the structure of the budget system of Uzbekistan, the subjects of Uzbekistan and municipalities, budget funds, extra-budgetary funds, the list of budget revenues, budget expenditures, as well as their distribution and redistribution between different budgets. Budget procedural norms are norms that regulate the procedure for drawing up, reviewing, approving, executing budgets and the procedure for drawing up and approving a budget execution report.

The general part of budget law consists of norms that fix the general principles, general methods of activity of state bodies of Uzbekistan, subjects of Uzbekistan, local self-government bodies, as well as the main powers of subjects of budget legal relations.

The legislative bodies exercise control over the execution of the budget. There are 3 forms of control: preliminary; current; subsequent.

The legislative body has the right to reject a report on the implementation of the budget that does not comply with the law, to apply to the prosecutor's office in order to bring the perpetrators to justice.

Budget planning is a scientifically based process of centralized distribution and redistribution of gross domestic product and national income during budget preparation for all parts of the budget system [5].

The economic essence of planning is the centralized distribution and redistribution of the value of gross domestic product and national income across all parts of the financial system, based on the national socio-economic development program of the state in the process of drawing up and executing budgets and extra-budgetary funds of different levels [5].

The principles of budget planning are: *регулируемости* regulation of budget issues by uniform legal norms - *направленности* targeted nature of the direction of budget funds; *непрерывности* continuity of annual budget planning; *стабильности* stability of financial indicators (tax rates, norms, estimates); - balance method.

The basics of budget planning are defined in the Constitution of Uzbekistan and in the laws of the state.

Budget planning is carried out by state authorities and management bodies [5].

The budget process is included in budget planning as its main form.

The budget process is the activity of the authorities regulated by law for the preparation, consideration, approval and execution of the central, regional and local budgets. The state and budgetary structure of the country, the budgetary rights of the relevant authorities and legal entities determine the content of the budget process.

The budget process includes 4 stages of budget activity: 1) preparation of the draft budget; 2) consideration and approval of the budget; 3) budget execution; 4) preparation of the performance report and its approval.

All these stages of the budget process are interrelated, interdependent and reflect both economic processes and the political culture of society.

The tasks of budget planning are as follows - организация organization of the preparation of financial plans, their coordination with the main directions of economic and social development; - determination of the full amount of financial resources, breakdown of these resources by various sectors and recipients of budget funds; - identification of the degree of participation of each of the subjects of the budget process in financial support, provision of funds for financing the development of territories, state events, etc.

Budget expenditure planning begins with the preparation of a draft budget by the executive authorities. The representative authorities make adjustments when considering the draft budget. The starting point of budget planning is the determination of the full amount of income that should go to the budget in the next year. The state can fully control expenses, unlike most income items, which depend on external conditions. These conditions include the volume of GDP, the size of the tax base, and the rate of economic growth. The state can regulate the tax rates, conditions and procedure for their collection, but the possibilities of change are limited, since this requires legislative procedures.

Budget expenditure planning is based on budget forecasting.

Forecasting requires an analysis of the already achieved indicators and taking into account the objective laws of different stages of economic development under different external conditions.

The main methods of budget planning are: balance method; economic and mathematical methods; method of economic analysis; normative; program-target; index; modeling methods; extrapolation method; forecasting method and others [6].

The main method in budget planning is the balance method, due to the fact that it reflects the content of the budget as the main balance of income and expenses [6].

Economic and mathematical methods make it possible to ensure the variability of solutions, to model the most optimal proportions.

Using the method of economic analysis, it is possible to compare planned and actual indicators, as well as to identify the main directions of the movement of budget funds, to reveal the reasons for incomplete collection of funds, to determine the degree of their effective use [6; 10].

The most used method in the Russian Federation is the normative method. It allows you to determine the target budget expenditures within the projected revenues [6].

To provide state target programs with funds, the program-target method is used [6].

The analysis of the dynamics of the inflation rate, the level of real wages, real incomes is the basis of the index method.

When using the modeling method, various conditions for the development of socio - economic processes are laid in the model. When choosing an erroneous forecast option, the modeling method can quickly correct the deviations produced [6; 10].

The extrapolation method uses the directions of development of past and current stages for planning future ones [6].

The expert forecasting method combines the analytical conclusions of experts and the available statistical data in forecasting. This method is used when it is impossible to reliably determine the development of socio-economic conditions from the outside [6].

The main share of budget expenditures at all levels falls on the financing of budgetary institutions. Financing is carried out on the basis of estimates.

The estimate is the main financial plan of a budget organization. It reflects the full amount of financial resources, the target direction of these resources, as well as their quarterly distribution. In this way, state authorities and management bodies, as well as institutions of the non – productive sphere-healthcare, education, social protection-are financed.

Budget institutions include expenditures in the budget estimates using the budget classification. These expenses of budget organizations include the same types of expenses that specify the use of budget resources: labor costs; payroll charges; travel payments and other payments that are provided for by law; transfers to the population; expenses for paying for goods, works and services under concluded contracts; economic expenses; capital expenses.

The detailing of budget expenditures is necessary for enhanced control over the targeted use of these expenditures by funding agencies.

The expenditures of the state budget are economic relations that arise due to the distribution of the fund of state funds and its use for the intended, sectoral and territorial purpose. The economic essence of budget expenditures manifests itself in a huge number of types of expenditures, each of these types can be characterized by a

qualitative and quantitative side. The qualitative characteristic determines the economic nature and social purpose of any type of budget expenditures, and the quantitative characteristic determines their value. Budget expenditures are divided into current ones, which provide for the current needs of the country, and capital ones, which provide for expanded reproduction, inventory growth, and more.

Budget planning of revenues, budget planning of expenditures is aimed, as a result, at drawing up a draft budget, in the direct preparation and execution of which all state authorities and management bodies participate.

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